

The Factors Affecting of Health Employee at Public Health Centre, Sentani Sub Province Jayapura

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ABSTRACT

Background: Performance of health workers is very important to improve community health status. Puskesmas Sentani as a basic health care facility in carrying out its duties is not yet maximal.

Research objective: to determine the factors that influences the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center Jayapura Regency

Research Method: Analytical cross sectional study design. The population is health workers at Sentani Health Center and a sample of 81 people with total sampling. Data were obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using chi square test and logistic binary regression.

Result of research : factors that influence the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center Jayapura Regency are work discipline (p-value = 0.003; RP = 2.357; CI95% = 1.367 - 4.065) reward (p-value = 0.020; RP = 2.553; CI95% = 1.110 - 5,869), punishment (p-value = 0,000; RP = 12,083; CI95% = 4,002 - 36,480) and leadership (p-value = 0,001; RP = 2,639; CI95% = 1,476 - 4,718). While the factors that have no effect on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center are age (p-value = 1,000; RP = 0.954; CI95% = 0.552 - 1.649), working period (p-value = 0.414; RP = 0.733; CI95% = (0.403 - 1.334) and motivation for the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.108; RP = 1.709; CI95% = 1.019 - 2.868).

Keyword: Performance, Health Workers, Public Health Centre

INTRODUCTION

First level health services unit and in the forefront health service system,

Puskesmas make mandatory health efforts and selected health efforts tailored to conditions, needs, demands, capabilities and innovations as well as local government policies. Its functions include as a primary health care center and also a center for community empowerment. As a center for primary health services affordability and ease of access to health care facilities is very necessary because it will affect the success of puskesmas in carrying out their functions (Ministry of Health, 2010).

Employee is one of the most important factors in determining progress an organization. According to Thompson (in Robbins, 2010) quality organization depends on the quality of the people in it. To get productive and high-achieving employees in the work, organizations are required to have reciprocal tools that are in line with performance each employee in order to get productive employees and the best performance in accordance with the expectations and goals of the organization.

Health workers are the most important assets that health services must have and need to be considered by management. Humans come from the fact that people (humans) are elements that are always present in the organization. Humans make goals, make innovations and achieve organizational goals. Human resources trigger creativity in every organization. Without the existence of effective human resources it would be impossible for the organization to achieve its objectives. Human resources make other organizational resources work (Simamor, 2012).

Professional employees can be interpreted as a view to always think, work hard, work full time, discipline, honest, high loyalty, and full of dedication for the success of their work.

Performance is someone's success in carrying out tasks, work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authority and responsibility or about how someone is expected to function and behave in accordance with the tasks assigned to him and quantity, quality and the time used in carrying out tasks (Sutrisno, 2010). To get optimal work results, one of them is leadership ability to direct employees to be willing do what the company wants. Leader in an organization, both profit oriented and non-profit oriented positions dominant in determining the back and forth of a company. That performance produced by a company is a description of the ownership of results given by the leader managing the company (Fahmi, 2013). A leader must develop an attitude in leading his subordinates. A leadership attitude can be formulated as a behavior pattern that is formed to be aligned with the interests of the organization and employees to be able to achieve the stated goals (Nasution (1994) in Riyadi, 2011). The role of the Head of Puskesmas is very important to move his subordinates to become a good work team through motivation, so that motivation can improve the performance of his subordinates such as being on time, care provided in accordance with procedures and documenting the patient's health development.

This opinion reflects how big the leadership role in an organization, so that a leader is expected to have reliable leadership skills so that organizational goals can be achieved. As for what is meant by the ability of a leader is the ability to motivate, influence, direct and communicate with subordinates. Besides that leaders must also have behaviors or ways of leadership that are adapted to the situation and conditions of the organization, which is

flexible, meaning being able to adapt or adapt to the subordinate's environment (Herlambang, 2012). Some health workers at Sentani Health Center show low work discipline seen from absenteeism, employees who arrive late, from observations and information obtained from the head of staffing department, it is still found that the enthusiasm for carrying out activities is still low, and this shows the low performance of some employees towards puskesmas. In this case the researcher wants to present seven factors, namely the factors of age, years of service, motivation, work discipline, reward, punishment and leadership of the Head of Sentani Health Center. This selection is based on the fact that the eight factors appear most often in theories that discuss factors that influence employee performance. Work discipline is a form of obedience from a person's behavior in complying with certain provisions or regulations relating to work, and is applied in an organization.

Therefore, in this research, researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "Factors that Affect the Performance of Health Workers in Sentani Health Center, Jayapura Regency, Papua Province"

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Type of Research

This study is an analytical study with a cross sectional study design that aims to determine the effect of two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2013). This study explains the relationship affects and is influenced by the variables to be studied. Using a quantitative approach because the data will be used to analyze the relationships between variables expressed by numbers or numerical scales (Sastroasmoro, 2010). This study analyzes the effect of age, years of service, work motivation, job rotation, work discipline, reward, punishment and leadership style of the Head of the Community Health Center on the performance of health workers.

2.2. Time and Location of Research

This research was carried out at the Sentani Health Center in January 2018

2.3. Population and sample

a. Population

The population in this study were all employees at Sentani Health Center as many as 90 people, of which health workers were 88 people.

b. Samples

The sample is part of the generalization of the population studied (Sugiyono, 2013). If the population is less than 100, then the sample size is the total population. The sampling technique uses a saturated sampling technique. Thus the sample size is 81 people, caused by 6 health workers who attended education and 1 head of the Puskesmas was not included as a sample.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Bivariate Analysis

a. Effect of age on the performance of health workers

Table 1. Effect of age on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Age	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	< 30 year	19	38,8	30	61,2	49	100
2	≥ 30 year	13	40,6	19	59,4	32	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 1,000; RP = 0,954; CI95%= (0,552 – 1,649)

Based on Table 1, it shows that out of 49 health workers aged <30 years as many as 19 people (38.8%) had poor performance and 30 people (61.2%). Whereas from 32 people aged >30 years health personnel, 13 people (40.6%) had poor performance and 19 people (59.4%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p*-value = 1,000 > 0.05. This means that there is no effect of age on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center which is not meaningful. The prevalence ratio test results are interpreted as age not risk factors for lack of performance of officers.

b. Effect of tenure on the performance of health workers

Table 2. Effect of tenure on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Working period	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	New	10	32,3	21	67,7	31	100
2	Old	22	44	28	56	50	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,414; RP = 0,733; CI95%= (0,403 – 1,334)

Based on Table 2, it shows that of the 31 health workers who had a new tenure of 10 people (32.3%) had less and good performance as many as 21 people (67.7%). While of the 50 health workers who had a long working period of 22 people (44%) had poor and good performance as many as 28 people (56%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p*-value = 0.414 > 0.05. This means that there is no effect on the working period on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center. The prevalence ratio test results are interpreted as a period of work not a risk factor for poor performance of officers.

c. Effect of motivation on the performance of health workers

Table 3. Effect of motivation on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Motivation	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	11	57,9	8	42,1	19	100
2	High	21	33,9	41	66,1	62	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,108; RP = 1,709; CI95%= (1,019 – 2,868)

Based on Table 3, it shows that of the 19 low motivation health workers, 11 people (57.9%) had poor and good performance as many as 8 people (42.1%). While from 62 high-motivated health workers, 21 people (33.9%) had poor and good performance as many as 41 people (66.1%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p*-value = 0.108 > 0.05. This means that there is no effect of motivation on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 1,709; CI95% = (1,019 - 2,868) interpreted that health workers who have low motivation are at risk of having a performance that is less

than 1,709 times higher than health workers who are highly motivated.

d. Effect of work discipline on the performance of health workers

Table 4. The effect of work discipline on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	work discipline	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	19	61,3	12	38,7	31	100
2	Good	13	26	37	74	50	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,003; RP = 2,357; CI95% = (1,367 – 4,065)

Based on Table 4 it shows that out of 31 health workers lacking work discipline there are 19 people (61.3%) who have less and good performance as many as 12 people (38.7%). While 13 of the 50 health workers with good work discipline (26%) had poor and good performance as many as 37 people (74%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p-value* = 0.003 < 0.05. This means that there is an influence of work discipline on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 2,357; CI95% = (1,367 - 4,065) which is interpreted that health workers who have less risk work discipline have less performance 2,357 times higher than health workers who have good work discipline.

e. Effect of rewards on the performance of health workers

Table 5. Effect of reward on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Reward	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	None	27	49,1	28	50,9	55	100
2	Exist	5	19,2	21	80,8	26	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,020; RP = 2,553; CI95% = (1,110 – 5,869)

Based on Table 5, it shows that out of 55 health workers who stated that there were no rewards as many as 27 people (49.1%) had less and good performance as many as 28 people (50.9%). Whereas from 26 health workers who stated that there were 5 people rewarding (19.2%) had less and good performance as many as 21 people (80.8%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p-*

value = 0.020 < 0.05. This means that there is an influence of reward on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center. When viewed from the value of Rp = 2,553; CI95% = (1,110 - 5,869) which was interpreted that health workers who did not have a risky reward had less performance 2,553 times higher than health workers who received rewards.

f. The effect of punishment on the performance of health workers

Table 6. The effect of punishment on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Punishment	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	None	29	80,6	7	19,4	36	100
2	Exist	3	6,7	42	93,3	45	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,000; RP = 12,083; CI95% = (4,002 – 36,480)

Based on Table 6, it shows that out of 36 health workers stated that there was no punishment as many as 29 people (80.6%) had less and good performance as many as 7 people (19.4%). Whereas 45 health workers stated that there were 3 people in punishment (6.7%) who had poor performance and 42 people (93.3%). The results of the chi square test obtained *p-value* = 0,000 < 0,05. This means that there is a punishment effect on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 12,083; CI95% = (4,002 - 36,480) which was interpreted that health workers stated that there was no punishment at the risk of having a performance less than 12,083 times higher than the health workers who were punished.

g. Influence of leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance of health workers

Table 7. The influence of the leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance of health workers at Sentani Health Center

No	Leadership of the puskesmas head	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	21	61,8	13	38,2	34	100
2	Good	11	23,4	36	76,6	47	100
Total		32	39,5	49	60,5	81	100

p-value = 0,001; RP = 2,639; CI95% = (1,476 – 4,718)

Based on Table 7, it shows that out of 34 health workers with the leadership of the Head of the Health Center lacking as many as 21 people (61.8%) had less and good performance as many as 13 people (38.2%). While from 47 health workers whose leadership of the Head of a good Puskesmas as many as 11 people (23.4%) had less performance and good as many as 36 people (76.6%). The results of the chi square test obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.001 < 0.05$. This means that there is influence of the leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance at Sentani Health Center. When viewed from the value of $RP = 2,639$; $CI95\% = (1,476 - 4,718)$ interpreted that health workers who have a less risky leadership style have less performance 2,639 times higher than health workers who state good leadership.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Effect of age on the performance of health workers

The results showed that there was no effect of age on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center ($p\text{-value} = 1,000$). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Barata (2013) in Puskesmas in Gianyar Regency that age does not have a significant relationship with the performance of officers. The age factor can affect one's physical and psychological strength and at a certain age an employee will experience changes in work potential. Senior employees tend to be satisfied with their work because they are better able to adapt to the environment based on their experience. They tend to be more emotionally stable, so that overall they can work more smoothly and regularly.

Age is the span of life span from birth and age (Handayani, 2010). Age will affect a person's physical condition, enthusiasm, burden and responsibility both in work and in daily life. For health workers who are less than 30 years old, despite having good physical condition, to carry out

physical activities but in general they have a relatively less sense of responsibility compared to those aged ≥ 30 years (Sandra, 2013).

The results of the analysis showed that the health workers who were <30 years old as many as 19 people (38.8%) had poor and good performance as many as 30 people (61.2%). Whereas from 32 people aged health workers >30 years as many as 13 people (40.6%) had less performance and good as many as 19 people (59.4%). This shows that the age of health workers aged <30 years and >30 years has equal opportunities for good or less performance. The absence of influence can be due to other factors that affect the performance of health workers not because of the physical age of health workers, but the environment in the health center such as the existence of rewards, so that health workers are not satisfied in work that affects the performance of health workers. Judging from the age limit of health workers aged >30 years the oldest is 47 years old and the youngest is 23 years old, so that physically does not affect the performance of health workers who are still in their productive age. The average health worker aged <30 years is a health worker with an employee honor status or contract, so that health workers will compete to create good performance so that they can be considered and become a priority in receiving civil servants. The same thing was done by health workers aged >30 years, most of whom were civil servants and had an influence on satisfaction and motivation for career divisions that were both good and equal - they were at risk of having good performance, so they did not affect performance.

This is in accordance with the theory proposed by Gibson (2003), that age has an indirect effect on individual behavior and performance. The older a person is, not necessarily able to show intellectual maturity both cognitively and psychomotor when doing work. This is probably due to the personal values of the individual

concerned, flexibility and other psychological factors that influence.

4.2. Effect of tenure on the performance of health workers

The results showed that there was no effect on the work period on the performance of health workers in the Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.414). The results of the same study were put forward by Lutiarsi (2013) in Semarang Regency, which states that years of work have no relationship with performance. Likewise the results obtained by Samsualam, Indar, & Syafar (2008) in Makassar state that there is no significant relationship between years of service and performance.

According to Robbins (2006) a person's tenure shows the level of seniority. Where the level of seniority is an expression of work experience. According to Sandra (2013), the longer a person's work experience, the more skilled the officer is, it is easy to understand their duties and responsibilities, thus providing an opportunity for achievement. The results of the analysis showed that the health workers who consisted of 31 health workers with a new tenure of 10 people (32.3%) had less and good performance as many as 21 people (67.7%). While of the 50 health workers who had a long working period of 22 people (44%) had poor and good performance as many as 28 people (56%). This shows that the working period of new and old health workers is equally at risk of having poor performance.

The absence of influence on the working period on the performance of health workers can be influenced by the existence of a reward or award given. Health workers who are not satisfied, especially health workers who have long worked, can affect performance. On the other hand, new health personnel, but feel satisfied with the work they get so they feel comfortable in their work which can improve performance. So that satisfaction in work is not influenced by the work period of health workers.

Past behavior that has become accustomed to behaving discipline and enthusiasm in working according to the process will most likely continue to behave accordingly in the future, and vice versa. So that it can be concluded that the old and new working periods expressed in work experience do not necessarily guarantee good performance if they are used to behaving inappropriately.

4.3. Effect of motivation on the performance of Health Workers

The results showed that there was no significant effect of motivation on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.100). However, low work motivation has a chance of performance that is less than 1.709 times higher than health workers who have high work motivation. The results of this study are in line with the Beratha study (2013) in the Gianyar District Health Center that there was an effect of motivation on the performance of health workers. Motivation is an act of a group of factors that cause individuals to behave in certain ways (Herlambang, 2012). Motivation teaches how to encourage subordinate work morale so that they want to work harder and work hard by using all their abilities and skills to be able to advance and achieve company goals. While the motivation is the driving force that results in an organization member willing and willing to time to organize various activities into his responsibility and fulfill his obligations in the number of achievement of goals and various organizational goals that have been determined previously (Siagian, 2010).

4.4 Statement of respondents about motivation in working with low motivation that each work or provide services to patients must require colleagues. This causes the independence of health workers to decrease. In other words, health workers have a high morale when they are equal to other health care colleagues. In addition, health workers do not feel proud of the

results of services that get appreciation from leaders or co-workers. This shows that the motivation of health workers seems to have other needs that must be considered by the health center management. While health workers who have high motivation are caused by always trying various alternatives to achieve success, good cooperation among friends encourages to work hard so that they can complete good work, make plans to achieve success, if they have difficulty doing something more like to try hard to finish it, feel satisfied when you get the best results and if it works well. In addition, health workers are confident in my ability to work well and provide services to patients quickly and try to be responsible for the work seriously to prepare themselves to face the challenges of work and get a promotion. This shows that health workers have the motivation to actualize.

Self-actualization is related to the process of developing one's true potential. The need to show the ability, expertise and potential of someone. Self-actualization needs have a potential tendency that increases because people actualize their behavior. A person who is dominated by the need for self-actualization likes tasks that challenge his abilities and expertise (Sofyandi and Garniwa, 2007). The results of the analysis showed that low motivation health workers were 11 people (57.9%) who had less performance and good as many as 8 people (42.1%). 21 highly motivated health workers (33.9%) had poor and good performance as many as 41 people (66.1%). This shows that health workers who are highly motivated have a higher proportion of performance. The prevalence ratio test results obtained that health workers who have low motivation are at risk of having a performance that is less than 1.709 times higher than those of health workers who are highly motivated.

The influence of motivation on the performance of health workers is due to the fact that health workers do their jobs well in the hope that they can fulfill their needs through promotion, so that they compete or

compete in obtaining promotions that affect the incentives or compensation they receive.

4.5. Effect of work discipline on the performance of health workers

The results showed that there was an influence of work discipline on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.003). The results of this study are in line with Salam's (2013) research at the Wara Selatan Health Center in Palopo City which revealed that the influence of work discipline on the performance of health workers. Hasibuan (2010) argues that discipline is the awareness and willingness of someone to obey all applicable company regulations and social norms. Based on the above understanding it can be concluded that work discipline is an attitude, behavior, and action that is in accordance with both written and unwritten rules, and if it violates there will be sanctions for violations. The respondent's statement about discipline is the lowest - the average return from work does not match the predetermined time, does not complete the task in accordance with a predetermined time and does not carry out the boss's orders properly.

According to Simamora (2012) discipline is a procedure that corrects or punishes subordinates for violating regulations or procedures. Work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change behavior and as an effort to increase one's awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable company regulations and social norms (Rivai, 2010).

The results of the analysis showed that there were 19 health workers (61.3%) who were underperforming and 12 were good (38.7%). Health workers with good work discipline as many as 13 people (26%) had poor and good performance as many as 37 people (74%). This shows that the health workers who are working are getting higher and better performance. This is evidenced from the results of the prevalence ratio test that health workers who have less work

discipline are at risk of having a performance less than 2,357 times higher than health workers who have good work discipline. Observations of researchers that the work discipline of health workers is influenced by employee morale, the level of compensation provided, thus affecting employee job satisfaction. Health workers who feel dissatisfied with the results of work with compensation provided, so they are not disciplined or comply with the rules set. To obtain the work discipline needed in the decision-making process, leaders can conduct discussions with subordinates so that problems that exist within the puskesmas and alternative actions can be identified. Leadership applied in decision making must be more flexible, because inappropriate decisions will invite risk. The risk needs to be considered more deeply, especially when decision makers will determine their decisions that have possibilities that must be achieved in the future.

4.6. Effect of rewards on the performance of Health Workers

The results showed that there was an effect of reward on performance in Sentani Health Center (p -value = 0.020). In line with the results of the Beratha study (2013), it was revealed that reward has an influence on the performance of health workers. According to Handoko (2010) Reward is a form of appreciation for businesses to get a professional workforce in accordance with the demands of a position that requires a balanced coaching, namely an effort to plan, organize, use, and maintain labor so that they can carry out tasks effectively and efficiently. As a concrete step in the results of coaching, rewards are given for employees who have shown good work performance.

Most health workers who feel they are lacking in the rewards state that health workers will be better at work if there are more incentives that I receive and feel very happy when given the task beyond the standard. Furthermore, health workers also

stated that some health workers were less involved because they felt they did not have authority over delegated tasks and prevented health workers from participating in the activities of the health professionals' professional organizations.

While health workers who feel good about the rewards given do new things related to work, feel given the opportunity to increase career paths and provide feedback about professional health issues. In addition, the guardian stated that the promotion was regulated in a fair regulation and given the same opportunity.

The results of the analysis obtained that health workers with no reward as many as 27 people (49.1%) had less and good performance as many as 28 people (50.9%). Health workers who have rewards as many as 5 people (19.2%) have less and good performance as many as 21 people (80.8%). This indicates that a lack of reward reduces the performance of health workers. The prevalence ratio test results obtained by health workers who did not have a risky reward had a performance that was less than 2,553 times higher than the health workers who were rewarded.

The influence of less reward given by management can reduce the performance of health workers. This shows that the Puskesmas leadership does not respect the contribution of health workers, especially health workers with honor status / contracts, so health workers have a feeling of unhappiness at work. This feeling of unhappiness creates a sense of indifference towards health workers in the puskesmas who feel they are not part of the place where they work, so that the performance of health workers decreases. Shown with low work responsibilities. To be able to improve the performance of health workers, it is necessary to make financial and non-financial compensation for health workers in contract / compensatory health personnel who are still perceived to be less than what is achieved.

4.7. Effect of punishment on the performance of Health Workers

The results of the study showed that there was an effect of punishment on performance in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0,000). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Salam (2013) at the Wara Selatan Community Health Center, Palopo City, which revealed that there was an effect of punishment on the performance of health workers. Punishment is a threat of punishment which aims to improve employee offenders, maintain applicable regulations and provide lessons to offenders "(Mangkunegara, 2010). Basically the purpose of punishment is so that employees who violate feel deterred and will not repeat again. Respondents' statements about punishment were felt that health workers felt they were not reprimanded for completing their assignments on time because they were reprimanded by their superiors and did not get suspended for making mistakes. While good punishment says getting a reprimand from the boss for coming late and feeling ashamed of other health workers because they get a warning from their superiors and try to improve my performance after getting a suspension. This shows that health workers who get punishment in the form of sanctions or penalties from the leadership increasingly enthusiasm in work.

The results of the analysis showed that health workers did not get punishment as many as 29 people (80.6%) had less and good performance as many as 7 people (19.4%). Health workers who received punishment as many as 3 people (6.7%) had less and good performance as many as 42 people (93.3%). This shows that the better punishment increases the better performance of health workers. This is evidenced by the results of the prevalence ratio test that health workers who are not punished are at risk of having a poor performance of 12,273 times higher than health workers who are punished.

The influence of punishment on improving employee performance is caused by an unpleasant act in the form of punishment or sanction given to health workers consciously when a violation occurs so as not to repeat it. This can be an incentive tool for employees to improve their performance.

4.8. Influence of leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance of health workers.

The results of the study showed that there was an influence of the leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance at Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.001). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Salam (2013) at the Wara Selatan Health Center in Palopo City, revealing that there was an influence of leadership style on the performance of health workers. According to Tjiptono (2006) leadership style is a way used by leaders in interacting with their subordinates. Meanwhile, another opinion states that leadership style is a pattern of behavior (words and actions) of a leader perceived by others (Hersey, 2004). Leadership style is the behavior or method chosen and used by leaders in influencing the thoughts, feelings, attitudes and behavior of the members of their subordinate organizations (Nawawi, 2011). Respondents' statements about leadership style are lacking, because the director does not provide examples that can increase interest in work and does not support subordinates' efforts to solve every work problem and does not use a positive personal approach with subordinates in carrying out tasks and does not encourage the need for group work in completing work . This shows that the Head of the Puskesmas Sentani lacks interaction or communication with his subordinates, including the problems faced. This can be caused by the director taking over the leadership of the head of the puskesmas, but it is still felt to be unsatisfied by health workers, because the aspirations or problems cannot be

resolved without the intervention of the director.

The statement of the respondents stating that the leadership style is well retained mostly tells the subordinates the details of the work through standard operating procedures for how the work must be completed. The Director also incidentally supervises the execution of subordinate duties and provides direction in accordance with his command line. The results of the analysis showed that the health workers with the leadership of the Head of the Health Center were less than 21 people (61.8%) had less and good performance as many as 13 people (38.2%). Health workers with the leadership of the Head of a good Puskesmas as many as 11 people (23.4%) had poor performance and 36 people (76.6%). This shows that better leadership by the Head of the Community Health Center can improve the performance of health workers in a high way. This is evident from the results of the prevalence ratio test that the leadership style is less noisy has less performance 2,639 times higher than the health workers who state good leadership.

From the results of this study it can be seen that, health workers who are given high support and two-way communication occurs between leaders and health workers in problem solving, the performance of health workers will be better As with health workers who do not interact enough so that delegates or leadership cannot felt directly by health workers in improving their performance. Conversely, health workers who often interact feel cared for by the leadership, so that all actions or work carried out are considered or supervised by the leadership, thereby increasing the morale of the health workforce.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. There is no influence of age on the performance of health workers in

Sentani Health Center (p-value = 1,000; RP = 0.954; CI95% = 0.552 - 1,649).

2. There is no influence on the working period on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.414; RP = 0.733; CI95% = (0.403 - 1.334).
3. There is no effect of motivation on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.108; RP = 1.709; CI95% = 1.019 - 2.868).
4. There is the influence of work discipline on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.003; RP = 2.357; CI95% = 1.367 - 4.065)
5. There is an effect of reward on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.020; RP = 2.553; CI95% = 1.110 - 5.869)
6. There is an effect of punishment on the performance of health workers in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0,000; RP = 12,083; CI95% = 4,002 - 36,480)
7. There is the influence of the leadership of the puskesmas head on the performance in Sentani Health Center (p-value = 0.001; RP = 2,639; CI95% = 1,476 - 4,718)

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